

Study on self-healing concrete and testing and evaluation of its mechanical properties

Md Abu Jaied Suruji^{1*}, Amadul Haque¹, Md Abdullah Shaikh¹

¹ Department of Civil Engineering, College of Civil Engineering and Architecture, China Three Gorges University, Yichang, China

Abstract: Concrete, as the most widely used artificial building material in the world, has many advantages such as high strength, good durability, and low cost. However, due to its low tensile strength, concrete is prone to varying degrees of microcracks, which reduces its durability. The application of microbial induced calcium carbonate precipitation (MICP) technology can effectively fill cracks and prevent further expansion. Exploring the influence of bacterial concentration and air entraining agent dosage on the mechanical properties and crack repair effect of self-healing concrete. The three-point bending experiment showed a significant improvement in the bending strength of concrete after curing and repair; The healing rate of concrete cracks increases with the increase of bacterial concentration and air entraining agent dosage; Taking into account both repair efficiency and strength recovery, it is recommended that the optimal bacterial concentration be 2×10^6 cells/mL, with an air entraining agent dosage of 0.01% of the cementitious material mass; Finally, phase analysis was conducted to verify that the crack filling material is calcium carbonate; The bonding repair between fibers and matrix improves the flexural strength after recovery, and summarizes the repair mechanism of fiber-reinforced concrete.

Keywords: Self-healing concrete; Bacillus subtilis; Bacterial concentration; Air entraining agent; Mechanical properties

*Corresponding Author

Accepted: 10 December, 2024; **Published:** 13 December, 2024

How to cite this article: Md Abu Jaied Suruji, Amadul Haque, Md Abdullah Shaikh (2024). Study on self-healing concrete and testing and evaluation of its mechanical properties. *North American Academic Research*, 7(12), 30-36. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14461517>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

Publisher's Note: NAAR stays neutral about jurisdictional claims in published maps/image and institutional affiliations.

Copyright: ©2024 by the authors. Author(s) are fully responsible for the text, figure, data in this manuscript submitted for possible open access publication under the terms and conditions of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY) license (<https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

Introduction

Due to its wide applicability, economic practicality, and high durability, concrete remains the most popular building material in the world. However, the larger self weight and lower tensile strength of concrete cause some cracks under external factors, such as plastic shrinkage cracks, hydration heat release, creep, and external loads. Researchers have attempted to immobilize microorganisms as a substitute for some aggregates in concrete and found that crack repair in concrete is significant. But how to effectively immobilize bacteria in concrete, while maintaining activity and having good self-healing effects without sacrificing concrete strength, is something that needs to be improved. So this article adopts the method of adding air entraining agents to create a suitable ecological niche for bacteria, and successfully explores a more suitable concrete mix proportion under the premise of different bacterial concentrations as variables. It was found that the self-healing of concrete cracks in the optimal state was significant, and the repaired concrete showed

a certain degree of strength recovery, revealing its self-healing mechanism and preparing for the combination with engineering cement-based composite materials (ECC).

ECC was first proposed by Li et al. [20] and has the characteristic of 3-5% strain capacity. Unlike typical local fractures of ordinary concrete, ECC exhibits multiple cracks under tension, and the average crack width can be controlled within 60-80 μ m. Although such a small crack width can further selfheal through the continuous hydration of unreacted cementitious materials. However, only when the crack width is less than 50 μ m, can the cementitious material completely fill the microcracks. If it exceeds 50 μ m, it will largely fail to heal. If wider cracks in ECC can heal more thoroughly on their own, it would be highly desirable. So adding bacteria to ECC in this article may provide another effective method to solve this problem. On the other hand, the addition of some bacteria may improve the matrix and fiber/matrix interface properties of ECC, thereby affecting the mechanical properties and strain capacity of ECC, which has become another focus of this study.

MICP is a new approach for repairing concrete cracks. Bacterial concentration is an important part of concrete mix proportions. On the one hand, different bacterial concentrations can affect the mechanical properties of concrete, and on the other hand, they have a direct relationship with crack repair. However, the pore space in concrete is limited, and the continued hydration during the curing process makes the pores denser, which puts greater pressure on the survival of microorganisms and affects the mineralization and precipitation ability of bacteria. The use of triterpenoid saponin air entraining agents creates tiny pores inside concrete to provide living space for bacteria, enabling them to maintain their activity effectively for a long time.

This paper aims to explore the application of *Bacillus subtilis* in the preparation of self-healing concrete, and further investigate the effects of bacterial concentration and air entraining agent content on crack repair performance. We mainly conducted three-point bending experiments to fabricate cracks at the bottom of fiber-reinforced concrete. Study the effects of four different bacterial concentrations, namely 0, 2×10^5 , 2×10^6 , and 2×10^7 cells/mL, on crack self-healing. In addition, the self-healing effect under different air entraining agent dosages (0, 0.005%, 0.01%, 0.015%, and 0.02% of the cementitious material mass) was also discussed. Finally, conduct phase analysis on the crack filling material to observe whether bacterial imprints are left on the surface of calcium carbonate.

2. Literature Review

In the United States, approximately 20 billion dollars are expended annually on the maintenance, repair, or replacement of deteriorating structures. In Europe, 50% of the yearly construction budget is allocated to maintenance and repair. Gardner et al. [3] identified that cracking in concrete was the predominant issue in a survey regarding challenges faced in concrete construction in the U.K. Although fissures in concrete structures typically do not pose a safety hazard, their existence hastens the ingress of corrosive agents like CO₂ and chlorides, leading to the deterioration of the reinforcement. Schlangen and Joseph indicated that the durability challenges related to concrete are substantial and will not diminish unless materials with self-healing properties are investigated and advocated [4].

Initially identified by the French Academy of Sciences in 1836 within water-retaining structures, the self-healing mechanism in concrete has been extensively and rigorously examined in the past decade. Interest in this subject has surged dramatically, with the volume of published papers increasing over tenfold from 25 to 281 between 2010 and 2020. The shift in attitudes towards sustainable solutions, coupled with the substantial costs associated with the maintenance and repair of concrete structures, drives research into materials with self-healing properties. This project examined concretes incorporating various admixtures (crystalline admixture CA, expansive agent CSA, superabsorbent polymer SAP) and their combinations to promote autogenous healing. These self-healing methods are more cost-effective and simpler to execute than encapsulated techniques.

Currently, a standardized testing method to assess self-healing in concrete has not been established. Extensive reviews on the experimental characterization of self-healing, including crack closure, durability, mechanical properties, and microstructure, have been published [6]. Assessing surface crack closure is the simplest method for evaluating self-

healing; however, this approach may result in either underestimation or overestimation of healing efficacy [8]. Experimental techniques reliant on transport or durability characteristics, such as water permeability, facilitate the assessment of entire crack volumes and therefore serve as suitable methods for evaluating self-healing. Experimental techniques focused on assessing the mechanical properties of concrete, including stiffness and strength, are crucial for identifying effective self-healing capabilities. Although the majority of studies examined self-healing efficacy through the restoration of durability properties [9], fewer focused on the recovery of mechanical properties [10].

3. Pouring of self-healing concrete

This chapter mainly explores the influence of *Bacillus subtilis* on the self-healing effect of concrete cracks. The self-healing mechanism or self-healing agent in concrete should ideally meet the following characteristics: (1) it should be able to seal or fill newly formed cracks to reduce the permeability of the concrete matrix and achieve true self-healing effect; (2) Compatibility with concrete, i.e. its existence should not have a negative impact on the material properties of concrete; (3) Due to the fact that the lifespan of concrete structures is usually at least 50 years, they should have long-term potential activity; (4) It is best to act as a catalyst and should not be consumed during this process to achieve multiple healings; (5) Having certain economic applicability to maintain the competitiveness of materials.

When preparing self-healing concrete, it is necessary to provide a certain living space for bacteria. In this experiment, an air entraining agent mainly composed of triterpenoid saponins was added to the concrete, which has better air entraining performance. The main purpose of air entraining agents in engineering is to generate many tiny bubbles in concrete, while improving the fluidity and frost resistance of concrete. The construction dosage is generally 1-8% of the cementitious material. But the higher the content of air entraining agent, the greater the impact on its compressive strength and flexural strength. Therefore, after adjusting the content of the air entraining agent in this experiment to 0-0.02%, the main purpose is to utilize its air entraining effect to generate tiny bubbles with a diameter of about 10-600 μ m inside the concrete, providing a certain ecological niche for bacteria. At the same time, such a small content can almost ignore the impact on the compressive and flexural properties of the concrete.

Polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) fiber is a synthetic fiber made of polyvinyl alcohol resin, which has the characteristics of good hydrophilicity, high strength, and low elongation. To prevent brittle failure of concrete during the precast cracking process and to control the crack width, PVA fibers are added to the concrete mortar to improve its ductility and facilitate observation and evaluation of crack repair in the later stage.

The self-healing agent mainly consists of *Bacillus subtilis* bacterial solution, 20 g/L calcium chloride solution, and 10 g/L urea, which replace a part of the water when pouring concrete.

4. Sealing evaluation of concrete cracks

4.1 Prefabricated crack treatment of test specimen

In practical engineering, cracks may easily occur in concrete due to structural design defects, foundation settlement, local stress, or delayed maintenance. Therefore, this experiment adopts a three-point bending test to simulate the cracks generated in actual situations, and further evaluates the self-healing ability of microbial concrete through curing and repair. This experimental instrument comes from the universal testing machine (WAW-300B) in the Basic Laboratory Building of Nanjing University of Science and Technology. The three-point bending test device is shown in Figure 1. The bottom of the concrete beam specimen is supported by two brackets with a span of 14 cm. At the same time, an extensometer is installed at the bottom of the concrete beam to record the displacement of the crack opening caused by force bending. To ensure quasi-static loading conditions, displacement control with a loading rate of 0.2 mm/min is used. Each loading experiment resulted in a crack of approximately 0.5 mm at the bottom, and in order to obtain the unloading response of the crack specimen, a slow reverse unloading was also performed. After the unloading experiment, a V-shaped crack appeared at the bottom of the beam. Due to the bridging effect of the fibers, the crack contracted a certain distance, and the maximum crack width was about 0.4 mm. Finally, record the load crack opening displacement curve for each three-point bending experiment.

4.2 Comparison of bending strength

The interior of the concrete matrix is in a highly alkaline environment, and as the curing time increases, the number of bacteria may sharply decrease. From the experimental curve, it can be seen that the load rapidly increases at the beginning, and the concrete is still in an elastic state, under the joint force of fibers and concrete. Then it suddenly drops after reaching the peak load, and cracks begin to appear at the bottom of the specimen. The concrete in the tensile zone exits work, and then the fibers bear the tensile force, gradually stabilizing the load. For better comparison, Figure 1b) shows the bending strength comparison corresponding to the peak strength of each specimen in 1 (a). The bending strength is calculated by $f_f = 3FL / (2bh^2)$, where F is the peak load; L is the span of the support; B and h are the width and height of the cross-section of the concrete beam.

Figure 1 Bending response of self-healing concrete under different bacterial concentrations

At the curing ages of 7 and 28 days, three-point bending experiments showed that the addition of bacteria would affect the flexural strength of concrete. In Figure 1 (b), compared to the control group, the flexural strength of concrete increases first and then decreases with the increase of bacterial concentration, and the peak strength of specimens at each bacterial concentration is improved. When the bacterial concentration is 2×10^6 cells/mL, the bending strength is the highest, at 5.08 MPa, which is 38.8% higher than the control group's 3.66 MPa; When the bacterial concentration was 2×10^5 cells/mL, the bending strength was 3.93 MPa, an increase of 6.9%; When the bacterial concentration was 2×10^7 cells/mL, the strength was almost the same as the control group, at 3.69 MPa. It can be summarized as under appropriate bacterial concentration, the MICP effect makes the interior of concrete denser, thereby improving its bending strength. Figure 1 (c) shows the bending response of concrete beam specimens after 28 days of curing. Due to the continued hydration of cement, the bending strength has significantly increased compared to early specimens, as shown in Figure

3.2 (d). When the bacterial concentration was 2×10^5 , 2×10^6 , and 2×10^7 cells/mL, the bending strength was 5.56 MPa, 5.76 MPa, and 4.65 MPa, respectively, which increased by 24.2%, 28.6%, and 0.6% compared to the control group's 4.48 MPa. In addition to hydration, the addition of bacteria also further enhances the bending strength of concrete. The maximum bending strength is achieved when the bacterial concentration is 2×10^6 cells/mL.

Figure 2 Bending response of self-healing concrete under the influence of different air entraining agent dosages. The optimal bacterial concentration has been confirmed to be 2×10^6 cells/mL. Based on this, the effect of the dosage of air entraining agent (0, 0.005%, 0.01%, 0.015%, and 0.02% of the cementitious material mass) on the flexural strength of concrete was studied (groups 5-9 in Table 3.1), as shown in Figure 2. Figure 2 (a) shows the bending response of early concrete beams under different amounts of air entraining agent, and Figure 3.3 (b) shows the bending strength corresponding to each peak load. Compared with the control group, with the increase of air entraining agent content, the bending strength of concrete first increases and then decreases. When the dosage of air entraining agent is 0.01% of the cementitious material, the bending strength is the highest, at 5.44 MPa, which is 16.99% higher than the control group's 4.65 MPa; However, when the dosage of air entraining agent increased to 0.02%, the bending strength was the lowest, at 4.21 MPa, a decrease of 9.46%. Figures 2 (c) and 2 (d) show the bending response curves and bending strength comparison of concrete under different air entraining agent dosages under 28 day standard curing conditions, respectively. Compared with the control group's 5.6 MPa, the flexural strength of concrete with 0.005%, 0.01%, and 0.015% dosage was 6.29 MPa, 6.42 MPa, and 6.12 MPa, respectively, an increase of 12.32%, 14.64%, and 9.29%. However, when the dosage of air entraining agent was 0.02%, the flexural strength was 5.46 MPa, a decrease of 2.5%. Therefore, the addition of air entraining agents within an appropriate range can improve the flexural strength of concrete, but when it exceeds 0.02%, the strength begins to decrease, possibly due to excessive porosity. Therefore, to further study

self-healing concrete, the most suitable amount of air entraining agent was set at 0.01% of the mass of the cementitious material in this experiment.

At the same time, the bending strength of healing specimens with different amounts of air entraining agents was compared, and the results are shown in Figure 3. Similarly, it can be observed that the bending strength after healing has increased compared to the remaining bending strength, as shown in Figure 3 (a). Except for the control group with a recovery rate of only 2.36%, the strength recovery rates of specimens with air entraining agent dosages of 0.005%, 0.01%, 0.015%, and 0.02% were 9.12%, 24.91%, 15.92%, and 4.96%, respectively, with an average strength recovery rate of 13.73%, as shown in Figure 3 (b). When the dosage of air entraining agent is between 0.01-0.015%, the strength recovery is good, which also means that within a certain range, an increase in the dosage of air entraining agent has an indirect effect on the strength recovery of self-healing concrete.

Figure 3: Recovery of flexural strength of specimens under the influence of different air entraining agent dosages Whether it is early curing or standard curing concrete, bacterial concentration has a certain effect on the flexural strength of self-healing concrete. Compared with the control group, when the bacterial concentration was 2×10^6 cells/mL, the bending strength was the highest at 5.08 MPa, which was 38.8% higher than the control group; After being cured and repaired, the bending strength of the concrete has also significantly improved compared to the remaining bending strength of the first time. When the bacterial concentrations were 2×10^5 cells/mL, 2×10^6 cells/mL, and 2×10^7 cells/mL, the strength recovery increased by 0.436 MPa, 0.469 MPa, and 0.21 MPa, respectively, with an average strength recovery rate of 16.05%. The addition of air entraining agents creates many tiny pores in self-healing concrete, providing an ecological niche for bacteria and increasing bending strength within a certain range. When the dosage of air entraining agent is 0.01% of the mass of the cementitious material, the bending strength is the highest, at 5.44 MPa, which is 16.99% higher than the control group; However, when the dosage of air entraining agent increased to 0.02%, the bending strength was the lowest, at 4.21 MPa, a decrease of 9.46%. After the specimens were cured and repaired, except for the control group which had a recovery rate of only 2.36%, the strength recovery rates of specimens with air entraining agent dosages of 0.005%, 0.01%, 0.015%, and 0.02% were 9.12%, 24.91%, 15.92%, and 4.96%, respectively, with an average strength recovery rate of 13.73%. When the dosage of air entraining agent is 0.01-0.015%, the strength recovery is better.

References

[1] V. Li, E. Herbert, Robust self-healing concrete for sustainable infrastructure, *J. Adv. Concr. Technol.* 10 (2012) 207–218.
 [2] E. Cailleux, V. Pollet, Investigations on the development of self-healing properties in protective coatings for concrete and repair mortars, presented at the, in: *Second International Conference on Self-Healing Materials*, 2009. Chicago, USA.

- [3] D. Gardner, R. Lark, T. Jefferson, R. Davies, A survey on problems encountered in current concrete construction and the potential benefits of self-healing cementitious materials, *Case Stud. Constr. Mater.* 8 (2018) 238–247.
- [4] E. Schlangen, C. Joseph, Self-healing processes in concrete, in: S.K. Ghosh (Ed.), *Self-healing Materials*, Wiley-VCH, Weinheim (Germany), 2009, pp. 141–182.
- [5] N. Hearn, Self-sealing, autogenous healing and continued hydration : what is the difference, *Mater. Struct.* 31 (1998) 563–567.
- [6] L. Ferrara, et al., Experimental characterization of the self-healing capacity of cement based materials and its effects on the material performance: a state of the art report by COST Action SARCOS WG2, *Construction and Building Materials*, Review 167 (2018) 115–142.
- [7] W. Tang, O. Kardani, H. Cui, Robust evaluation of self-healing efficiency in cementitious materials - a review, *Construct. Build. Mater.* 81 (2015) 233–247.
- [8] B. Park, Y.C. Choi, Self-healing capability of cementitious materials with crystalline admixtures and super absorbent polymers (SAPs), *Construct. Build. Mater.* 189 (2018) 1054–1066.
- [9] M. Roig-Flores, F. Pirritano, P. Serna, L. Ferrara, Effect of crystalline admixtures on the self-healing capability of early-age concrete studied by means of permeability and crack closing tests, *Construct. Build. Mater.* 114 (2016) 447–457.
- [10] K.-S. Lauch, C. Desmetre, J.-P. Charron, New water permeability set-up and factors affecting concrete self-healing, *Construct. Build. Mater.* 294 (2021), 123595.

